

1ST SECURENET 2023 WORKSHOP

Registration, Agenda & Speakers

Date	11 September 2023
Time	08:30 AM - 05:00 PM CEST
Location	UCD University Club UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN DUBLIN, IRELAND

What is it about?

The SECURENET 2023 workshop is an academic event jointly organized by Network Softwarization and Security Labs (NETSLAB) research group at the UCD School of Computer Science and SFI CONNECT Centre. It will be focussed on the future of security and privacy in 5G, 6G, and IoT Systems.

Who will participate?

The workshop is intended to bring together professors, researchers, graduate students, and Industrial researchers to share ideas, experiences and implementations related to the Security and Privacy aspects of 5G, 6G and IoT Systems.

